

NONLINEAR FE FORMULATION OF RADIAL TIRES WITH REFINEMENTS OF CONSTRAINT CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

A radial tire structure in contact with a flat foundation and mounted on a rigid rim is analyzed with a 3-D finite element method concerning geological nonlinearity either under inflation state or under footprint loading. A combination of Newton-Raphson method, following-load method and wave-front method is employed in the formulation to make the numerical simulation more realistic. The concept of incremental slip constraint is suggested to refine the constraint conditions so that more reasonable results can be obtained when incremental slip constraint is used especially in describing the hooping effect between the bead area and the rim. The program's reliability and convergency are fairly good and the computational results agree well with available experimental data.

Keywords: variable contact boundary, incremental slip constraint, hooping effect

1. INTRODUCTION

A radial tire is a complex structure made up of several kinds of composite materials(Figure 1), such as its bead, belts and carcass plies. When under loading conditions, the tire undergoes very large deformation and shows obvious nonlinearity. The constraint conditions also vary with the loading process, which makes the tire structure analysis very difficult. Sophisticated calculations are needed to predict a realistic stress and strain field of a tire because of the complexity of its geometry, anisotropy of its composite components, large deformations, nonlinear mechanical behavior and various loading conditions[1][2]. In this paper, a new finite element analysis method that is based on

Figure 1 The Composite Components of a Radial Tire Structure

the large deformation theory and that involves comprehensively Newton-Raphson method, following load method and wave front method is used. Emphasis will be placed on the determination of the tire-foundation interaction and the fine adjustment of the tire-rim interface constraint, which is often neglected by previous works on tire analysis. Thus the exact contact boundary between the tire and the foundation can be determined together with the whole displacement field and the hooping effect of the bead on the rim can also be considered reasonably. A break-down and restart technique is used to avoid accidental losses when a sudden power-off occurs during the long and tedious computation process.

2. FORMULATIONS

2.1. Large deformation theory

To describe the deformation of the tire, we define the map

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}(\mathbf{X}) \quad (1)$$

The Green strain \mathbf{E} and Poila-Kirchhoff stress \mathbf{S} can be expressed respectively as:

$$E_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial x_k}{\partial X_i} \frac{\partial x_k}{\partial X_j} - \delta_{ij} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$S_{ij} = \frac{\partial X_i}{\partial x_j} \Sigma_{j1} \quad (3)$$

Coefficients exist between the stress and strain:

$$S_{ij} = D_{ijk1} E_{k1} \quad (4)$$

Generally speaking, \mathbf{D} is a function of \mathbf{E} . A tire is a complex structure with many different components. An isotropic behavior is generally assumed for the rubber parts and the reinforcements (plies, belts) can be modeled as transversely isotropic. In the present paper, all the coefficients of the constitutive equation are deduced from material testing [3].

2.2. Basic equations of the nonlinear FE method [4][5][6]

Green strain can be expressed in terms of displacement as follows:

$$E_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial X_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial X_i} + \frac{\partial u_k}{\partial X_i} \frac{\partial u_k}{\partial X_j} \right) \quad (5)$$

The discrete form of the equilibrium equation is:

$$\int_{V_0} B^T S dV_0 - \int_{V_0} N^T P_0 dV_0 + \int_{A_0} N^T Q_0 dA_0 \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{p}_0 and \mathbf{q}_0 are body force and surface traction defined on the original configuration respectively.

Suppose that K_T is the tangential stiffness matrix of the nonlinear equations, it can be formed as:

$$K_T = K_L + K_N + K_S \quad (7)$$

Where K_L , K_N , K_S are defined respectively as:

$$K_L = \int_{V_0} B_L^T D_T B_L dV_0 \quad (8)$$

$$K_N = \int_{V_0} (B_L^T D_T B_N + B_N^T D_T B_N + B_N^T D_T B_L) dV_0 \quad (9)$$

$$K_S = \int_{V_0} G^T M G dV_0 \quad (10)$$

2.3. Newton-Raphson method

The finite element approximation leads to a group of nonlinear equations. The main idea to solve them is to linearize the loading process gradually by iterative method.

A nonlinear equation

$$\Psi(\mathbf{u}) - \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{u}) - \mathbf{R} = \mathbf{0} \quad (11)$$

can be solved approximately in the algorithm below:

$$\Psi(\mathbf{u}^{n+1}) - \Psi(\mathbf{u}^n) + \left(\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{u}} \right)_n = \mathbf{0} \quad (12)$$

Where

$$\mathbf{u}^{n+1} - \mathbf{u}^n + \Delta \mathbf{u}^n \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_T = \left(\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{u}} \right)_n \quad (14)$$

Thus

$$\Delta \mathbf{u}^n = -\Psi(\mathbf{u}^n) [\mathbf{K}_T(\mathbf{u}^n)]^{-1} - [\mathbf{K}_T(\mathbf{u}^n)]^{-1} [\mathbf{R} - \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{u}^n)] \quad (15)$$

Where $\mathbf{R} - \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{u}^n)$ is the off-balance force of the nth iterative step.

In the practical calculation process, Newton method and incremental method are often incorporated together to overcome the deviation of the digital solution.

2.4. Wave-front method[7]

One of the most prominent difficulty in tire analysis is that a lot of CPU time and memory is needed in program running. So wave-front method is introduced to realize the large scale numerical simulation on a microcomputer like Micro-VAX I.

2.5. Following load method

The internal pressure of the radial tire is not a conservative force and its effect varies with the spatial configuration of the tire's internal surface element. Therefore the equivalent nodal load must be altered in each revisionary or incremental loading step.

2.6. Varying constraint conditions

Both of flat foundation and rigid rim enforce unilateral constraint on the tire, which means:

- a. The surface traction is non-negative
- b. The contact surface is non-penetrable

So the contact constraint conditions must be altered in each step until a rational boundary is obtained simultaneously with the accurate displacement field.

2.6.1. The determination of the unknown contact constraint

The contact area between the tire and the flat surface and the distribution of the contact forces are unknown a priori. An initial contact boundary is assumed (Fig.2) and a unilateral constraint is given for all the boundary nodes. Incremental constraint is introduced and revisions are made in the calculation after each iterative step when irrational contact force or penetration occurs.

Let Γ_c be the candidate contact surface of the structure and \mathbf{n} the exterior normal in Γ_c . The reaction force of a constrained node is expressed by its normal and tangential components as:

$$\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{r}_T + \mathbf{r}_N \quad (16)$$

When $\mathbf{r}_N \cdot \mathbf{n}$ the node is released from the contact area; when a free node penetrates into the surface of the flat foundation it is added to the contact area.

2.6.2. The incremental slip constraint of the tire-rim interaction

Little is mentioned in the literature about the hoop stress of the bead after a tire is mounted. Usually a fixed contact boundary is assumed. Because the diameter of the tire toe is slightly smaller than the rim seat, the bead has to extend circumferentially and therefore will hoop tightly on the seat of the tire's toe when mounted. Since the modulus of the bead is much higher than that of the surrounding rubber, obviously this assumption will result in severe errors of stress calculation in the bead area. In order to give a realistic deformation field of the bead area, the incremental slip constraint method is developed. By using this method, a higher convergent accuracy can be reached than by other methods, for example, the penalty coefficient method.

As can be seen from Figure 3, the candidate boundary nodes must be given enforced constraint displacement in the beginning of the computation. The difference between \mathbf{X}_1 and \mathbf{X}_1 is the initial constraint. Afterwards incremental slips of the contact node on the rim surface should be ascertained before each computation step. Suppose that $\Delta \mathbf{u}_{slip}$ is the incremental slip of constraint displacement, then it can be determined as follows:

$$\Delta \mathbf{u}_{slip} = 0 \quad \text{when} \quad |\mathbf{r}_T| \leq |\mathbf{r}_N| \cdot \mu \quad (17)$$

Figure 2 The Initial Contact Boundary between the Tire and the Flat Foundation

Figure 3 The Initial Configuration of the Tire Toe and the Rim

$$\Delta u_{slip} = -r_T \cdot \mu' \quad \text{when } |r_T| > |r_N| \cdot \mu \quad (18)$$

Where μ is a coefficient of friction and μ' is a positive number. If $\max(|\Delta u|_{slip}, |\Delta u|) \leq \epsilon$ is met, the calculation is convergent.

2.7. Break and restart technique

A break-down and restart technique is devised in the program so that losses can be avoided when an accidental power-off occurs, this enables the computation to be carried out even on super microcomputers.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 4 The Original Configuration and 2D Mesh of the Tire

Figure 5 The Deflected Configuration of the Last Cross Section of the Tire

footprint loading is analyzed. Due to the symmetry of its structure and the loading conditions, only a quarter of the tire is

considered. This part is evenly divided circumferentially into 10 sections, ranging from 0° (top) to 180° (bottom).

Figure 6 The Deflected 3D Configuration of the Tire

Figure 7 The Stress of the 1st Carcass Ply

Correspondingly, there are 11 cross sections, labeled from 1 to 11. Two kinds of 3D elements are used: 8-node brick isoparametric element and 6-node isoparametric element. There are 1870 elements, 2310 nodes. The vertical deflection in computation is 2cm. Fig.4 shows the FE mesh of the tire cross section. Fig.5 gives the comparison between the computed deflected configuration of the last cross section and the contour measured in experiments. It can be seen that the two agree well with each other. In Fig.6 the whole deformed 3d tire is plotted. The stresses in the reinforced direction of carcass plies, steel belt are given respectively in Fig.7, Fig.8 and Fig.9. The vertical solid lines represent the end position of each component's element. The lateral coordinate indicates the meridian direction of the tire's cross section (from the center of the tread to the toe). Since the stresses of the first 6 cross sections are almost identical, only 5 curves are plotted with the number of cross section labeled.

Figure 8 The Stress of the 2nd Carcass Ply

4. CONCLUSIONS

A nonlinear three dimensional analysis using isoparametric elements is necessary for a tire under inflation and footprint loading to understand the basic mechanisms involved in the deformation of the tire. Various kinds of methods and techniques are needed to make the simulation process more practical and accurate so that steady and convergent results can be obtained.

Figure 9 The Stress of the Belt

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